

DEVELOPMENT OF AN IMPREGNATION TECHNIQUE FOR GLASS FIBRE MATS TO PROCESS TEXTILE REINFORCED CEMENTITIOUS COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

A controllable impregnation of glass fibre structures used in textile reinforced cementitious composites can nowadays only be obtained at laboratory scale by hand lay-up means, hindering possible structural applications of this promising composite. This paper will discuss a recently developed impregnation technique.

Keywords: cement composites, glass fibres, textile reinforcement, impregnation, processing technique

INTRODUCTION

Although they offer attractive properties, cementitious materials, as well as ceramics and glasses, are inherently brittle and present a modest and unreliable tensile strength. As such, they are unsuited for structural applications. Cements have a crucial advantage above ceramics and glasses: they are “cold setting”, which means they can easily be strengthened by various reinforcements. A conventional mean of reinforcement is strengthening this brittle material with steel rebars inevitably leading to mostly massive building elements that often eliminate sleek and light architectural design, a concept re-introduced in the past decades with both architectural and structural benefits. Examples of this concept, like lightweight steel structures or tensile architecture, are often neglected due to their weak insulating properties and limited fire resistance. A merge of both technologies where a cement based matrix gets reinforced with diverse textile fibrous materials could in some cases be a solution.

Future applications of these fibre reinforced cementitious composites (FRCC) all require a high fibre volume fraction (FVF) in order to resist to considerable high tensile forces. This high fibre volume fraction (above 10%) leads, after the onset of matrix cracking, to an additional load bearing capacity, also called strain hardening. Cement matrix composites, which exhibit strain hardening behaviour accompanied by multiple cracking, are defined as high performance fibre reinforced cement composites (HPFRCC). Although HPFRCC provides a limited stiffness, its ultimate tensile strength can be as much as mild steel. Figure 1 illustrates this strain hardening with the stress-

strain behaviour of a cement composite reinforced for a varying FVF (chopped strand mat, E-glass)^[1].

Figure 1: Influence of FVF on tensile behaviour (chopped strand mat, E-glass)^[1]

Common manufacturing processes for cement composites, like spray-up and pultrusion, seem however unable to satisfy this requirement, and thus actually limit the use of FRCC for building applications to (quasi-)non load bearing elements like infill wall panels, exterior cladding, etc.. Indeed, with FVF of around 5%, the load bearing capacity in tension is not exceeding the one of the non reinforced matrix, which is around 5 MPa. Hand lay-up, with its known disadvantages of low volume (and thus high cost) production, is at present the only valid processing technique to obtain a higher FVF.

In order to provide a substantial strain hardening for FRCC with an attractive industrial processing technique, the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) developed a self compacting impregnator (SCI) to pre-process the impregnation of a textile fabric with a cement matrix. The resulting wet prepreg contains a fibre volume fraction which can reach 25%, 3 to 10 times higher than the conventionally used spray-up technique for cement composites.

This paper will quantify the impregnation quality of a laminate produced by SCI by testing its mechanical properties distributed over the width of the production unit and by comparing it to specimens produced by hand lay-up means.

SELF COMPACTING IMPREGNATOR^[2]

Working Principle

If various manufacturing processes for cement composites are analysed, it can be seen that they share similar problems. Due to a high viscosity of the non-Newtonian cement matrix, fibre bundle impregnation can often not be obtained in a satisfactory way. Furthermore, the fibre structure will activate a filtering process between liquid and solid components of the matrix, leading to non equilibrated distribution of the reactivity and mechanical properties of the matrix. These two phenomena cause a weak fibre bond with early fibre debonding

and pull-out as a failing mechanism, thus eliminating high fibre stresses. Low composite strengths in tension or bending are a consequence.

The SCI eliminates these issues by pre-impregnating the textile reinforcements by pressing the matrix in a controlled, uniform and continuous way through the textile structure.

The working principle is shown in Figure 2. Two cylinders are rotating in opposite sense around parallel horizontal axes, leaving only a limited opening between their surfaces. This creates, between their upper half surfaces, a receptacle filled with fresh matrix mixture, which is continuously consumed during the rotation of the cylinders. The surface of the cylinders is grooved, in order to press the matrix mixture through the textile fabric at the point of smallest distance between the cylinders, where a pressure is obtained. As such, two or more textile structures are continuously impregnated, with the cylinders controlling the speed of production through a movable support.

Figure 2: Working principle of the Self Compacting Impregnator (SCI).

After impregnation, the semi-finished product, or “wet prepreg”, can then for example be pultruded or compressed without encountering the problems mentioned above. Furthermore, when this process is repeated and wet prepregs are placed on top of each other until a desired thickness is obtained, plates can be produced in a continuous way. By this means, the SCI compacts the laminate by pressing the produced wet prepregs together^[2].

MATERIAL TESTING

Fabrication

The laminates, used in the experiments, are glass fibre reinforced cement composites. The matrix component is IPC (Inorganic Phosphate Cement), a cement developed at Vrije Universiteit Brussel and commercialised under the name of VUBONITE. It is

composed of an inorganic phosphate liquid and a calciumsilicate solid. One of the advantages of using IPC rather than any other cement is that, due to its neutral pH after hardening, it does not attack standard E-glass fibres. As reinforcement a Chopped Strand Mat (E-glass) with a surface density of 300 g/m² is used in all laminates (VETROTEX M5).

Two laminates of 600 by 600 mm composed of 8 individual fibre mats have been produced by SCI by compacting 4 sets of pre-impregnated mats (Figures 3,a-b-c). For evaluation means, the matrix-fibre ratio has been kept constant for all laminates: a fibre ratio of 20% (± 1) in volume was pre-determined.

After production, the laminates were covered by hardboard plates, on which weights (± 100 kg) were applied to obtain a minimum of pressure. All specimens were produced at ambient conditions. The curing conditions were equivalent for all laminates: after 1 day of curing in ambient conditions, the weights were removed and the laminates were post-cured at 60°C in a Heraeus oven for 24 hours while evaporation was avoided. After curing, the test specimens were obtained using a water fed circular saw with diamond blade.

Figure 3,a: SCI

Figure 3,b: SCI

Figure 3,c: laminate

Tensile test

The tensile tests have been performed on an INSTRON 5885 universal test machine with a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min. A 50 mm double averaging clip-on extensometer determined the strain level whereas a load cell was used to monitor the stress level. The dimensions of samples were approximately 300 by 25 mm with a thickness of about 5 mm. The samples are pneumatically clamped at both ends. Table 1 indicates the results for the HLU reference sample ^[1]. The results of the samples produced by SCI are given in table 2 and figure 4 for the longitudinal specimens and in table 3 and figure 5 for the perpendicular specimens.

The pre-cracking stiffness is dominated by the stiffness of the matrix and it has been

computed in between 0,005% and 0,02% of strain as in this range the behaviour was seen linear for all tested specimens. After cracking, the behaviour of the composite is essentially dependent on the characteristics of the fibres. To calculate the slope of the stress-strain curve in post-cracking stage, a range from 0,4% up until 0,6% was defined. The composite failure stress is the maximum stress of the composite whereas the fibre failure stress is the stress present in the fibre at failure.

	specimen r1	specimen r2	specimen r3	Average	STDEV
FVF	19,7	19,9	20,1	19,9	0,2
pre-cracking stiffness [GPa]	17,3	17,5	13,8	16,2	2,1
post-cracking stiffness [GPa]	5,0	5,1	4,4	4,8	0,4
composite failure stress [MPa]	50	50	55	51	3
fibre failure stress [MPa]	707	706	898	770	110

Table 1: Tensile test results for HLU reference sample ^[1]

	specimen 1	specimen 2	specimen 3	Specimen 4	Average	STDEV
Width	25,2	25,1	25,1	25,4	25,2	0,2
thickness	4,6	4,6	5,0	4,8	4,8	0,2
FVF	20,4	20,4	18,7	19,6	19,8	0,8
pre-cracking stiffness [GPa]	12,8	13,1	12,1	13,0	12,7	0,4
post-cracking stiffness [GPa]	3,8	4,0	4,0	4,4	4,1	0,3
composite failure stress [MPa]	49	51	51	54	51	2
fibre failure stress [MPa]	715	748	819	825	775	54

Table 2: Tensile test results for longitudinal specimens

	specimen 5	specimen 6	specimen 7	Specimen 8	Average	STDEV
width	25,5	25,7	25,6	25,5	25,6	0,1
thickness	5,0	5,1	5,0	5,0	5,0	0,04
FVF	19,0	18,6	18,8	18,8	18,8	0,2
pre-cracking stiffness [GPa]	11,9	11,4	12,2	12,5	12,0	0,5
post-cracking stiffness [GPa]	4,3	4,0	4,2	4,2	4,2	0,1
composite failure stress [MPa]	48	49	53	54	51	3
fibre failure stress [MPa]	760	795	844	857	814	45

Table 3: Tensile test results for perpendicular specimens

Figure 4: Tensile test results for longitudinal specimens

Figure 5: Tensile test results for Perpendicular specimens

It can be seen that the maximum composite stress is very similar for both production techniques. Both pre-cracking and post-cracking stiffness are lower for SCI impregnating technique which indicates a weaker matrix fibre bonding. In longitudinal direction the specimens show the tendency to loose post-cracking stiffness along the width of the production unit. This is due to a non equal pressure distribution in between both cylinders. The specimens in perpendicular direction nearly don't show any variation. Nevertheless, regarding the aspect of strength, the self compacting impregnator produces plates of nearly equal quality as the time consuming and expensive hand lay-up technique.

Figure 6: HLU vs SCI

Both production techniques however lead to different cracking behaviours (Figure 6). To quantify the experimental difference in behaviour during this multiple cracking phenomenon, all test results have been curve fitted with a theoretical model.

Extending a proposal of Curtin et al^[3], Cuypers et al^[4,5] proposed a statistical treatment of matrix crack evolution in textile reinforced cements, assuming a Weibull distribution function to describe the stochastic distribution of the matrix strength. The Stochastic Cracking (SC) model is based on a two parameter Weibull distribution to describe the matrix strength of textile reinforced cements. The actual crack spacing x at a composite stress σ_c is related to the final (fully saturated) crack spacing X by the following formula:

$$x = X \left[1 - \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_{Rc}} \right)^m \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

with:

σ_{Rc} = reference cracking composite stress: first Weibull parameter, which is a measure of 'average' multiple cracking stress in the composite;

m = Weibull modulus: second Weibull parameter, indicating the width of the strength distribution.

Another calculated parameter is $\tau X/r$, which describes the force transmitted (shear stress = τ) between two cracks (crack distance = X) per unit fibre (fibre radius = r). It is a measure for the intensity of load transfer between fibres and matrix. Results are presented in Table 4 to 6.

	specimen 1	specimen 2	specimen 3	Average	STDEV
σ_{Rc} [MPa]	9,0	9,1	9,0	9,0	0,1
m	2,9	3,0	3,7	3,2	0,4
$\tau X/r$	164	164	171	166	4

Table 4: SC parameters obtained via curve fitting for HLU specimens

	specimen 1	specimen 2	specimen 3	specimen 4	Average	STDEV
σ_{Rc} [MPa]	5,8	5,2	5,6	5,8	5,6	0,3
m	3,6	2,6	2,7	2,7	2,9	0,5
$\tau X/r$	138,0	134,0	118,0	116,0	126,5	11,1

Table 5: SC parameters obtained via curve fitting for longitudinal specimens

	specimen 5	specimen 6	specimen 7	specimen 8	Average	STDEV
σ_{Rc} [MPa]	4,8	3,9	3,9	3,9	4,1	0,5
m	3,3	3,1	4,1	3,1	3,4	0,5
$\tau X/r$	124,0	124,0	134,0	130,0	128,0	4,9

Table 6: SC parameters obtained via curve fitting for perpendicular specimens

The parameter mostly influenced by the production process is σ_{Rc} . The specimens produced by SCI clearly share a lower reference cracking stress. This could be caused by a weaker fibre matrix bond compared to the one achieved by hand lay-up. The difference is also indicated in the $\tau X/r$ parameter: the intensity of load transfer is clearly higher for specimens produced by hand lay-up means, leading to a finer crack pattern. It can be suspected that this difference is originating in the different magnitude of compaction pressure of the impregnated textiles. This pressure is much higher with hand lay-up than for the SCI specimens, which were not compression moulded after impregnation.

CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical behaviour of laminates produced by the Self Compacting Impregnator has been compared to the one of laminates produced by the standard hand lay-up. As it is observed it can be said that the quality reaches on many fields the quality obtained by hand lay-up. Without any after treatment, like compression moulding or pultrusion, it must be said that the bonding achieved by this prototype is less than the one obtained using hand lay-up. A well regulated and high pressure build-up between the cylinders will ameliorate this shortcoming. Nevertheless, as a first step in a production process it delivers satisfactory results; in an industrially efficient way, a clean and well balanced impregnation of the fibres has been achieved.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The help of the European Union, through partial funding by project N° 26574 (6FP - Contex-T, Textile Architecture, Textile Structures and Buildings of the Future), is gratefully acknowledged.

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